

Improved tracking and docking of Industrial Mobile Robots through UKF vision based kinematics calibration

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Abstract—Performing an open-loop movement, or docking, for an industrial mobile robot (IMR), is a common necessary procedure when relying on environmental sensors is not possible. This procedure precision and outcome, solely depend on the IMR forward kinematic and odometry correctness, which is tied to the kinematics parameters, depending on the IMR kind. In this work, we focus on the so-called kinematic parameter calibration, using an unscented Kalman filter to estimate the geometrical kinematic parameters of a mobile platform. The mobile platform is externally tracked during the calibration phase, using a fixed temporary external sensor that retrieves the position of a visual tag fixed to the platform.

Index Terms—Mobile robot calibration, Unscented Kalman filter

I. INTRODUCTION

The odometry correctness impacts all use cases of an IMR, such as docking, in which we cannot rely on localization algorithms, high precision relative displacements, mapping and localization. Generally, the constant parameters that are taken into account in an IMR kinematic are the wheels radius, and a geometric length that depends of the IMR structure. Works dealing with the topic of parameter estimation and calibration are vastly present in literature, from a classical Denavit – Hartenberg approach [1], to rejecting-sampling methods [2], and Kalman filtering based methods, such as in [3], [4]. For an extensive survey, refer to [5] for a general overview, and to [6] for IMRs odometry calibration methods. The contribution of this work is to propose the usage of an external sensor system to track the IMR state, using a visual tag fixed on it, while reading the values of the wheels encoders, in order to perform a model parameter identification using the collected data, by means of an unscented Kalman filter.

II. BACKGROUND

A. mobile platform kinematic and odometry

Consider a generic IMR, where W is the globally fixed world frame, MR is the frame fixed to the IMR, and T_{MR}^W is the transformation matrix, composed by the rotational R_{MR}^W and translational $\mathbf{t}_{MR}^W = [p_x \ p_y \ p_z]^T$ parts, from the MR frame to the W . The robot position in the world is hence described by the six element vector $[p_x, p_y, p_z, \phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3] = [\mathbf{p}_W, \phi_W]$.

The IMR model generally includes the wheel radius r_j , a geometric distance depending on the robot kind l , and the wheels rotational speed. The IMR velocities \mathbf{v} and $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ at time t are expressed with respect to the MR frame as the vector $\mathbf{v}_{MR}^t = [v_x^t, v_y^t, v_z^t]^T$ and the transported in W frame to compute the odometry.

B. Unscented Kalman Filter

Kalman filtering theory can be optimally used in linear dynamical systems to estimate the state value, while, in case of a nonlinear system, variants of the original filter exist, such as the extended Kalman filter (EKF) or the Unscented Kalman filter (UKF). Considering the strong non-linearity of the system, and the additional complexity brought by the hand-eye problem, an UKF is employed, due to its increased reliability in non-linear system identification [7], and robustness to parameter initial value [8] due to the usage of the unscented transform [9].

III. METHODOLOGY

The system is comprised by an IMR endowed with wheel encoders, a visual tag fixed on the platform, and an external tracking camera to estimate the position of the visual tag. The system model includes the IMR kinematic and odometry, the tag frame position, the fixed transformation between the IMR frame and the tag frame, and the geometrical parameters related to the kinematic formulation.

Four reference systems are defined prior to the model, the frame W , a fixed global frame to which the mobile platforms position are referred, equal to MR , the mobile platform frame, at the starting time, and VW , the visual world fixed reference system, equal to V , the tag frame, at starting time, refer to Fig 1 for a system representation.

Hence, defining $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}$ as the tag-IMR transformation parameters and $\tilde{\mathbf{c}}$ as the tag-camera transformation, the state of the system becomes :

$$\left[\mathbf{v}_W \ \mathbf{p}_W \ \tilde{\mathbf{c}} \ \tilde{\mathbf{h}} \ \mathbf{r} \ l \ \mathbf{q} \right]^T \quad (1)$$

The measurable output y^t of the system is the visual tag position, computed by an external tracking system.

Figure 1: Coordinates systems in two different instant times.

IV. TEST CASES

A. Design of Experiments

Tests have been performed on two different IMRs, one omnidirectional and one with differential drive, along 10 paths, with the nominal path as the one measured by the camera. All the data are logged during the runs, and then used offline to evolve the dynamic of the discrete-time system. Parameters relative to the UKF are tuned according to [9], [10]. The identification algorithm is run in two different forms:

- parallelly, performing an estimation for each of 5 estimation data sets, using 10 iterations of the whole data per run, for then taking the average of the values.
- on the 5 data sets in series, for 10 iterations, for having a single estimate of the parameters.

To measure the performance improvements, 2 indexes will be used, one that takes in account the whole movement along the paths, and one which aim is to measure the docking precision. We define a path $\mathcal{P} = \{\mathbf{p}_0, \dots, \mathbf{p}_{N_p}\}$ as an ordered collection of IMR positions \mathbf{p} , where each position is composed by two translation(x, y) and one rotation(ω). Then, we will define a nominal path \mathcal{P}_n , as the one measured by the external camera, an original path \mathcal{P}_o , as the one computed using the initial parameters values of the IMR kinematics, and a corrected \mathcal{P}_c path, as the one re-computed with the newly estimated parameters. We compare the different paths, using the summation of the euclidean distance between each j -th point $\mathcal{P}(j) = p_j$ in \mathcal{P}_o and \mathcal{P}_c , with respect to the j -th point in \mathcal{P}_n as:

$$\mathcal{E}_o = \sum_j^{N_p} \|\mathcal{P}_n(j) - \mathcal{P}_o(j)\| \quad \mathcal{E}_c = \sum_j^{N_p} \|\mathcal{P}_n(j) - \mathcal{P}_c(j)\| \quad (2)$$

where N_p is the equal number of points of the paths, for then computing the percentage improvement of the corrected path as

$$\sigma_c = \frac{\mathcal{E}_o - \mathcal{E}_c}{\mathcal{E}_o} \quad (3)$$

B. Results

The results are presented in Table II for the omniwheel robot, and in Table III for the Turtlebot3 waffle, where Std refers to the standard deviation of the estimated parameter, and $\bar{\sigma}_c, \bar{r}$ and \bar{l} are the mean values, over the 50 trials. Results

concerning the docking, using the same concept as in 3, are shown in I.

Table I: Docking performance

$\bar{\sigma}_c$ (eq 3)	Parallel	Series
Omnidwheel	0.76	0.82
Turtlebot3	0.37	0.51

Table II: Omniwheel robot estimation results, on 20 trials

	Parallel	Series
\bar{r} [m]	0.101	0.104
$Std r$ [m]	0.0031	0.00035
\bar{l}_{xy} [m]	0.495	0.525
$Std l_{xy}$ [m]	0.0086	0.0017
$\bar{\sigma}_c$ (ref eq 3)	0.26	0.428

Table III: Turtlebot3 estimation results, on 20 trials

	Parallel	Series
\bar{r} [m]	0.027	0.031
$Std r$ [m]	0.0064	0.004
\bar{l}_d [m]	0.332	0.340
$Std l_d$ [m]	0.021	0.012
$\bar{\sigma}_c$ (ref eq 3)	0.122	0.27

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENT

An UKF vision based, mobile robot calibration algorithm is devised and tested in this work. The gathered results show a positive outcome, and the navigation and docking error is noticeably decreased after the calibration.

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